

Blockchain Technology in Waste Management to achieve Circular Economy

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Introduction

With increasing waste generation, sustainable waste management takes paramount importance as waste disposal methods that are being efficiently followed are not environmentally friendly mainly due to the general attitude of people despite creating public awareness. Recent advancement in Artificial Intelligence(AI) and blockchain technology have aided significantly towards waste management. This essay is an effort to discuss the role of blockchain technology as an enabler in waste management and hence help accelerate towards achieving a circular economy. The Circular Economy(CE) is characterized as "an economic system that replaces the 'end-of-life' paradigm with minimizing, alternatively reusing, recycling, and recovering materials in production/distribution and consumption processes," according to Kirchherr et al. (2017). Described as a "digital, decentralized, and distributed ledger in which transactions are documented and added in chronological sequence with the aim of producing permanent and tamperproof records"(Rejeb et al., 2018).

Blockchain plays a crucial role in establishing a circular model by monitoring the movement of the generated waste. Several industries, including finance, medical, energy markets, and transparent, censorship-resistant computers, use blockchain technology and distributed ledger (DLT). In-depth research into the DLT has been done since the emergence of blockchain and digital currency. In the context of bitcoin, the blockchain notion is self-evident. The architecture of bitcoin is represented by the sequential connection of blocks and the related transactional data carried by blocks. Each block's hash is incorporated into the header of the following block, making it tamper-proof and unchangeable. A network where nodes compete with one another to mine a block is facilitated by the sequential chain of blocks. The ledger is duplicated on each node. As a result, the blockchain network makes it simple to track down any change or alteration. Development of blockchains with generalized functionality Turing complete computation now makes it theoretically possible for blockchain computers to directly perform the entire spectrum of computational science, quantum chemistry, and physics simulations that are currently possible using conventional computers (Magnus, 2022).

Blockchain technology can help track the amount of waste that is collected, the information about who gathered it, the area from whence it was collected, and the current and end locations of the waste. A route and schedule to collect the waste can be developed using the data gathered by the sensors and saved on the blockchain in order to reduce the fuel consumption rate of the vehicles and increase the amount of waste collected each trip. The authorities can ensure that the filled waste bins are promptly collected by authorized users due to the high visibility and transparency of the garbage collection activities and sensor data. If the smart contracts determine that the wastebin's storage capacity has decreased, they can send a notification to the truck drivers.

The pilot program launched by diamond tycoon De Beers in January of 2018 to train and equip artisanal diamond miners in Sierra Leone before verifying and purchasing their products is a pertinent illustration of the usage of blockchain for a better ethical supply chain. Blockchain technology has the potential to usher in the next industrial revolution, bringing

with its new business models for the banking, supply chain, transportation, sharing economy, and many other sectors (Building a Sustainable Battery Supply Chain: Is Blockchain the Solution?, 2018).

State of the art

Based on Ahmad et al.'s research (2021), this section provides in-depth analyses of current blockchain-based projects as well as case studies that mostly center on digitizing waste management activities:

1. Recerream (RCM) is an Ethereum-based system that rewards citizens with money for sorting household waste at the waste source. It intends to make it possible for citizens to profit from every recycled bottle, battery, bottle, or piece of electronic equipment in an efficient and transparent way. When individuals drop off rubbish at a recognized location, such as a bottle vending machine, a station for collecting recyclables, or a waste collection center, the RCM coins can be placed in their wallets. The citizens may use these currencies to make payments for any services, including power, that they may be using. The blockchain in RCM has various uses, including supply chain management, rapid and automated payment settlement, and smart contract-based waste verification. Those who contribute rubbish can verify and trace it using the supply chain feature. It can also help in the discovery of goods made from the rubbish that citizens have sent in.
2. Swachcoin has utilized numerous cutting-edge technologies to successfully manage residuals and industrial trash for converting it into usable items. It has adopted smart contracts built on Ethereum, similar to Recerream, to determine and distribute rewards to citizens for recycling their waste. Swachcoin provides both token-based and flat-based ways to reward consumers for correctly managing their waste. The Swachcoin blockchain stores the transaction information on the open Ethereum platform. For maximum transparency and easy auditing, it also saves additional data on the blockchain, such as machine logs and prescriptive analytic reports.
3. To foster trust in the recycling industry's supply chain, RecycleGO has partnered with Deep Dive Technologies Group. In order to verify, track, trace, and report on operations in recycling supply chain businesses, it has made use of the Hyperledger Fabric platform. It utilizes smart contracts that are implemented on the blockchain to connect participants, such as buyers, suppliers, shippers, recyclers, and other supply chain actors, to the recycling services. This increases visibility for better decision-making. It can help to keep track of plastic bottles from the time they are manufactured until they are recycled and turned back into the raw materials for making new goods. In addition to helping with supply chain operations, it also helps recyclables haulers take the best route because they are integrated with a fleet management and route optimization system.

Context

The world is witnessing a boost in Electric Vehicle(EV) adoption hence resulting in concerns about raw materials in Lithium-Ion Batteries(LIBs) developing. The LIB has a changeable price depending on the availability and location of raw materials because their extraction has a considerable negative influence on the environment, especially with the lithium, nickel, aluminum, manganese, copper, graphite, and cobalt that are only found in a few areas of the world(Carlos et al., 2022). Inflation in the price of these minerals and EV batteries may result from the rise in demand for these types of materials, which could limit the adoption of EVs as a low-emissions form of transportation. The vast number of batteries that will reach the end of their useful lives and can be recycled, reused, or disposed of in landfills is another issue that society, researchers, and the productive sector are concerned about(Carlos et al., 2022). Sadly, the majority of batteries are still disposed of in landfills since, at the current state of development, the recycling process is still unable to handle a sizable amount of LIBs.

EVs might become more affordable with the help of used batteries, which would increase the market share of clean and renewable energy production systems and further the decarbonization of national energy grids. When integrated with renewable energy generation systems, used batteries can lessen the unpredictability of these systems and enable the storage of excess energy for use during periods of low energy generation. Moreover, used batteries can be quite helpful for providing power in isolated locations and can be incorporated into EV charging stations, enhancing the infrastructure for these vehicles' charging.

An EV user can return the batteries so that it can be recycled or reused, this demonstrates how the supply chain for batteries can also be circular. A number of businesses such as Bebat and DSO Fluvius and Energy Web have concentrated their efforts on streamlining and simplifying supply chain management(Smart Energy International, 2021). Knowing the origins and history of a product is crucial for market participants because it enables them to turn data into information, create projections and estimates, and categorize batteries according to their quality. The stakeholders or potential beneficiaries of this technology are the general public, government, private companies, community owners and designated members of the state. The actions of the stakeholders involved are commensurate with the efficiency of this technology.

Analysis

Blockchain technology is ideal for resolving issues where the competing interests of the various ecosystem entities are present. This technology makes it possible to develop intelligent, unchangeable contracts that specify business rules, enhancing supply chain security and transparency(Carlos et al., 2022). According to Carlos et al.'s study, blockchain technology can be used to track batteries throughout their supply chain, which will make it possible to address a number of issues in the battery sector(2022).

Emerging technologies that attempt to address industry issues include blockchain technology, which aims to disrupt several aspects of industrial and societal processes by offering a distributed, immutable, and validated repository of data that can trace the whole supply chain. Data from sensors will be gathered using the blockchain to monitor items and operations almost instantly. Locations, timestamps, voltages, currents, and temperatures are just a few examples of the types of data that will be stored using a distributed, immutable, and secure technology (Carlos et al., 2022). This technology also ensures a distributed validation of incoming data using protocols that have been agreed upon by the involved actors. Battery producers, system integrators, users, businesses that specialize in second-life applications, suppliers of raw and recycled materials, public control organizations, and many more parties are all involved in the battery market (Carlos et al., 2022). Furthermore, these actors may be from different nations and have competing interests, making them vulnerable to a variety of regulatory frameworks. In this context, the blockchain emerges as a potent mechanism for maintaining battery digital identities and tracking their lifecycle. The blockchain will track and trace the history of these significant values, including their second lives, recycling, and disposal, from the extraction of raw materials through production to the usage of batteries in electric propulsion (Carlos et al., 2022). In the case of batteries, this value has three components: the intrinsic value of batteries and their rare components and minerals, the value of trusted data related to battery life, and the environmental value in preventing the release of pollutants. Blockchain is the ideal technology for tracking and tracing values and valuable goods.

On following Ahmad et al.'s research (2021), some of the challenges of using Blockchain technology in battery recycling identified are:

- **Security:** Hackers frequently use reentrance attacks, integer overflows, denial of service attacks, and remote code execution to take advantage of smart contracts' common weaknesses. In light of this, it is crucial to thoroughly analyze the smart contracts before deploying them using advanced security analysis tools, such as Smartcheck, ReGuard, OYENTE, Mythril, Securify, and GASPER, to name a few.
- **Slow Adoption:** The integration of blockchain technology into the battery recycling sector is still in its infancy, despite the many benefits it offers and the existence of several open-source projects for trash management as noted in the essay.

Point of interest

Since blockchain technology is still relatively new, there aren't many publications or scientific journals that discuss its application to battery tracking. Understanding how battery tracking via a blockchain-based platform may assist businesses in adhering to technical standards and legal requirements is one of the key drivers behind this essay.

According to the Batteries Directive, only batteries with a carbon footprint claim can be sold as of June 1, 2024 (Green Deal, 2020). The increase in the battery collecting rate, which went from 45% to 65% in 2025 and 70% in 2030, is another aspect of the

regulation(Green Deal, 2020). This directive also defines other criteria such as the necessity to declare the content of cobalt, lead, lithium and nickel contained in batteries, as well as the minimum recycled content of these metals in the battery(Green Deal, 2020). It is important to understand blockchain-based systems and how these systems can support businesses in adhering to the laws and regulations necessary to comply with this directive and other requirements.

Following Carlos et al.'s study, given that blockchain technology still has a high cost in comparison to other technologies on the market, it is necessary to justify its application in various battery market scenarios(2022). Finding out whether a blockchain-based platform could be created is crucial to understanding how this technology can address issues like tracking the raw material's quality and origin to prevent shortages, keep prices stable, and ensure the desired level of purity, ensuring that the batteries meet the requirements for quality, performance, and safety for the application, knowing how a blockchain-based platform can help eliminate uncertainty and specify who will be the battery's maker, user, and owner at various points in its useful life is important and lastly making sure that the manufacture, usage, reuse, and recycling processes are as efficient as possible and that the supply chain is circular(Carlos et al.).

Conclusion

This essay is an effort to discuss the use of blockchain technology to leverage managing wastes and battery recycling in a manner that is decentralized, secure, traceable and trustworthy. Cities that are expanding and developing require the use of blockchain. Many blockchain-based and IoT-enabled pilot projects are currently being implemented in a number of different industries, including healthcare, agriculture, trade, finance, and others(Ahmad et al., 2021). Many benefits of blockchain technology, including safety, authenticity, transparency, and immutability, need to be explored with an eye toward resolving issues in the battery market. Despite several advantages, there are still certain questions that need to be answered because the technology is still new and unknown to the society at large.

Currently, laws and regulations surrounding blockchain are still in their infancy, which limits how easily technology can be used in the waste management sector. Finally, organizational elements that strongly affect the adoption of blockchain into battery recycling and waste management within smart cities include training facilities, top management support, perceived cost of investment, and accessible human resources(Ahmad et al., 2021).

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